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3 **1 Title**

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5 2 Hot or not? Conveying sensory information on food packaging through the spiciness-shape
6 3 correspondence

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9 **4 Author names and affiliations**

10 5 Ignacio Gil-Pérez ^a

11 6 Rubén Rebollar ^a

12 7 Iván Lidón ^a

13 8 Javier Martín ^{b, c}

14 9 Hans C.M. van Trijp ^d

15 10 Betina Piqueras-Fiszman ^d

16 11 ^a Departamento de Ingeniería de Diseño y Fabricación, Escuela de Ingeniería y Arquitectura,
17 12 Universidad de Zaragoza, c/ María de Luna 3, C.P. 50018 Zaragoza, Spain

18 13 ^bDepartamento de Estadística, Universidad de Salamanca, c/ Espejo 2, C.P. 37007 Salamanca, Spain

19 14 ^cBiostatistics Unit-IBSAL, Instituto de Investigación Biomédica de Salamanca, Paseo de San Vicente
20 15 58-182, 37007 Salamanca, Spain

21 16 ^d Marketing and Consumer Behaviour Group, Wageningen University & Research, Hollandseweg 1,
22 17 6706 KN Wageningen, The Netherlands

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31 **18 Corresponding author**

32 19 Ignacio Gil-Pérez

33 20 Tel.: +34 976 761910; fax: +34 976 762235.

34 21 E-mail address: inakigil@unizar.es (I. Gil-Pérez).

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39 **22 Abstract**

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41 23 The packaging of a product is a key element in the communication between producers and
42 24 consumers, so getting the consumer to interpret the packaging visual signs in the desired way is
43 25 crucial to be successful in the marketplace. However, this is not easy as images can be ambiguous
44 26 and may be interpreted in different ways. For example, depicting an icon of fire on the front of a bag
45 27 of nuts may lead the consumer to interpret either that the nuts are spicy or that the nuts have been
46 28 roasted. This paper addresses this problem and, using this case as an example, assesses if the
47 29 interpretation of a fire icon (spicy vs roasted) can be modulated by manipulating its shape (angular vs
48 30 rounded). 66 participants carried out an experiment which results show that there is a crossmodal
49 31 correspondence between spiciness and pointy shapes and that this association can be used to
50 32 modulate sensory expectations: in a speeded classification task, the bags of nuts depicting pointy fire
51 33 icons were categorised more quickly as being spicy than as being roasted, while the opposite was
52 34 true for the bags of nuts displaying rounded fire icons. In addition, the results of a mediation analysis
53 35 suggest that this effect occurs indirectly through affective appraisal: the pointy fire icons were judged

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1 as being more aggressive than the rounded fire icons, which in turn raised spiciness expectations.
2 These findings contribute to the research on crossmodal correspondences and semiotics by showing
3 that the association between spiciness and abstract shapes can be used to modulate how people
4 interpret an ambiguous image.

5 **Keywords**

6 Semiotics; Expectations; Categorisation; Packaging design, Implicit measures

7 **Highlights**

- 8 • There is a crossmodal correspondence between spiciness and pointy shapes.
- 9 • That association can be used to modulate consumer sensory expectations.
- 10 • On a bag of nuts, a pointy (rounded) fire icon evokes spicy (roasted).
- 11 • Fire icon's shape effect on expectations is mediated by aggressiveness perception.
- 12 • Both pointy shapes and spiciness are perceived as aggressive stimuli.

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121 **1. Introduction**
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123 2 One of the main tasks of a packaging designer is to effectively communicate the characteristics of
124 3 the product contained within, as packaging is an important communication tool between producers
125 4 and consumers (Nancarrow, Wright, & Brace, 1998). To that end, the designer must understand and
126 5 untangle the codes and language used by consumers (Frascara, 1988; Laing & Masoodian, 2016)
127 6 and, in addition, reproduce them clearly in an appealing design (Silayoi & Speece, 2007). Images
128 7 allow the designer to both communicate messages and gain aesthetic quality, which is why they are
129 8 frequently used in food packaging (Underwood & Klein, 2002). Images are a key element in the
130 9 packaging visual appearance as they allow the consumer to quickly identify and categorize the
131 10 product (Loken, 2006) and to generate expectations about it (see Deliza & MacFie, 1996; Piqueras-
132 11 Fiszman & Spence, 2015, for reviews). However, for the designer it is not easy to anticipate the
133 12 meaning that a consumer will assign to an image since in a given context an image can evoke
134 13 different concepts (Smith, Barratt, & Selsøe Sørensen, 2015): for example, when viewing an icon
135 14 depicting fire on a bag of nuts the consumer may interpret that the nuts are spicy or that the nuts
136 15 have been roasted. For both designers and producers it is key to know what does the elicitation of
137 16 one meaning or another depend on, as previous works suggest that for a product to succeed in the
138 17 market it should satisfy consumer expectations (Piqueras-Fiszman & Spence, 2015). The
139 18 investigation reported here addresses this problem by studying if it is possible to use the crossmodal
140 19 correspondence between spiciness and shapes to favour one of the possible interpretations of the
141 20 same image, which would allow the designer to gain control over the communication process.
142 21 Specifically, we argue that the meaning implicitly assigned to an icon of fire depicted on a bag of nuts
143 22 (i.e. spicy or roasted) depends on the angularity of the icon, and propose that the nature of this effect
144 23 is affective.

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152 **2. Background**
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154 2.1. The image displayed in the package as a propositionally indeterminate semantic sign
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156 26 The visual appearance of a package plays a key role during the categorisation process and the
157 27 generation of expectations, since consumers use the different elements of the package as signs from
158 28 which to infer information (Loken, 2006; Loken, Barsalou, & Joiner, 2008). Based on Peirce's
159 29 semiotics (1991), Ares et al. (2011) distinguish two kinds of signs in the context of food packaging:
160 30 linguistic signs (i.e. signs that produce meaning by social convention, like texts or words) and visual
161 31 signs (i.e. signs that produce meaning by resemblance, like colours or images). Today we have
162 32 abundant information regarding the way in which linguistic signs or some visual signs such as colour
163 33 influence these processes (Kauppinen-Räsänen & Luomala, 2010; Lähteenmäki, 2013; Piqueras-
164 34 Fiszman & Spence, 2015; Spence & Piqueras-Fiszman, 2014; Sütterlin & Siegrist, 2015). On the
165 35 contrary, the specific effect of the images in the communication between packaging and consumer
166 36 has been less studied. For example, Smith et al. (2015) showed that having an image on the
167 37 package of the major taste-giving ingredient instead of a text description makes consumers believe
168 38 there is a greater proportion of it in the product, while Rebollar et al. (2016) showed that products
169 39 accompanied with the main product in the serving suggestion depicted on a package of fresh cheese
170 40 influence the time of the day it is considered most suitable to consume it. More recent work from the
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180 1 same team suggest that communicating that the potato chips contained in a package had been fried
181 2 in olive oil by showing an image of an oil dispenser instead of by stating it by a text increases the
182 3 sensory, non-sensory and hedonic expectations of the product and increases the willingness to buy it
183 4 (Rebollar et al., 2017).

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186 5 However, despite the importance of transmitting a clear and unambiguous message to the consumer,
187 6 the designer cannot easily anticipate the meaning that will be inferred from an image displayed on a
188 7 food package. An image by itself is propositionally indeterminate and may evoke many
189 8 interpretations in the mind of the consumer, since it lacks the syntactic devices necessary to emit an
190 9 explicit propositional meaning (Messaris, 1994, 1997; Smith et al., 2015). For example, consider the
191 10 case of depicting an image of fire on a bag of nuts: the consumer may interpret that the product is
192 11 spicy or that the product has been roasted (Smith et al., 2015), as in this context *fire* may be
193 12 congruently understood in either way. Although this propositional indeterminacy can be broken by
194 13 making the meaning of the image explicit by using supporting text (Barthes, 1977; Phillips, 2000), the
195 14 paths by which the meanings of text and image are decoded are different and can lead to different
196 15 interpretations. In that case, an additional process is required to resolve the conflict and select a
197 16 definitive meaning (Lewis & Walker, 1989), which may negatively affect the processing fluency and
198 17 the overall attitude toward the product (Alter & Oppenheimer, 2009). In addition, it is also worth
199 18 noting that the image captures attention faster than the text (Honea & Horsky, 2012; Silayoi &
200 19 Speece, 2007; Venter, van der Merwe, de Beer, Kempen, & Bosman, 2011), is processed more
201 20 quickly (Mueller, Lockshin, & Louviere, 2009; Underwood & Klein, 2002), and that the first impression
202 21 may condition the response to subsequent stimuli (Epley & Gilovich, 2006; Madzharov & Block,
203 22 2010). Thus, effectively controlling the expectations evoked by the image is thus crucial for the
204 23 designer in order to ensure that the message conveyed by all the signs displayed on the package is
205 24 congruent.

206 25 2.2. Conveying spiciness through the shape of an image

207 26 The literature dedicated to crossmodal correspondences gives a hint about why it can be expected
208 27 that the shape of an image depicted on a food package may influence the sensory expectations of
209 28 the product contained within. Crossmodal correspondences are the often surprising associations that
210 29 the majority of people seems to share across stimuli from different sensory modalities (Spence,
211 30 2011). Although many of the studies that initially analysed these effects focused on the
212 31 correspondences between audition and vision (Parise & Spence, 2013; Spence, 2011), crossmodal
213 32 correspondences have been documented among all sensory modalities (Spence, 2011). Specially
214 33 regarding the gustatory sense, it has been shown that expected and perceived flavour may be
215 34 influenced by audition (see Spence, 2015a for a review), touch (Barnett-Cowan, 2010; Piqueras-
216 35 Fiszman, Harrar, Alcaide, & Spence, 2011) or vision. In this particular case, associations have been
217 36 found between both flavour and taste and cues as colour (Piqueras-Fiszman & Spence, 2011;
218 37 Piqueras-Fiszman, Velasco, & Spence, 2012), packaging shape (Becker, van Rompay, Schifferstein,
219 38 & Galetzka, 2011; Velasco, Salgado-Montejo, Marmolejo-Ramos, & Spence, 2014) or abstract
220 39 shapes (Liang, Roy, Chen, & Zhang, 2013; Velasco, Woods, Petit, Cheok, & Spence, 2016).
221 40 However, the majority of the research conducted to date has focused in basic tastes and other

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239 1 components of flavour like the burning sensation of spiciness/piquancy¹ have been barely studied
240 2 (Wang, Keller, & Spence, 2017).

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243 3 Literature makes a clear distinction between the concepts of taste and flavour (Spence, Smith, &
244 4 Auvray, 2014). While the basic tastes include bitter, sweet, salty, sour and umami, and are
245 5 understood as the specific gustatory sensations that occur with the stimulation of receptors located in
246 6 the tongue (Delwiche, 1996), flavour is a more complex multisensory perception that is processed
247 7 from gustatory, olfactory (mainly retronasal) and trigeminal inputs (Spence, Smith, & Auvray, 2014;
248 8 Spence, 2015). The trigeminal system is the chemosensory system responsible of mediating
249 9 sensations as the cool feeling caused by peppermint chewing gum, the tingling produced on the
250 10 tongue by carbonated drinks or the burning sensation while eating chili peppers (Lundström,
251 11 Boesveldt, & Albrecht, 2011). The spiciness/piquant sensation that arises when you eat chili peppers
252 12 or other pungent products is therefore produced by the activation of the trigeminal system receptors
253 13 located in the mouth when the irritants contained in these products, such as capsaicin, are released.
254 14 These receptors are the same ones that are responsible for processing temperature, pain and
255 15 chemical irritation, so the sensation produced by capsaicin is processed by the brain in similar terms
256 16 to those of an increase in temperature (Caterina, Schumacher, Timinaga, & Rosen, 1997). The
257 17 intensity of the perceived heat depends on factors such as the concentration of capsaicin present in
258 18 the food (Baron & Penfield, 1996), time elapsed between intakes (Carstens et al., 2002) or serving
259 19 temperature (Reinbach, Toft, & Møller, 2009), and usually takes a few tenths of a second to reach its
260 20 maximum level (Prescott & Stevenson, 1995). Although the spiciness/burning sensation produced by
261 21 capsaicin is not considered a basic taste, it is described as a significant contributor to flavour
262 22 perception and has even been described as “the forgotten flavour sense” (Lawless, 1989; Spence,
263 23 2015b; Tu, Yang, & Ma, 2016; Viana, 2011). As is the case with other flavour components, people
264 24 seem to match spiciness with stimuli from other sensory domains such as audition and vision. Thus,
265 25 both expected and perceived spiciness can be enhanced with specific sound attributes (high pitch,
266 26 fast tempo or high levels of distortion; Wang et al., 2017), by manipulating the intensity of red
267 27 colouring of a salsa (the more intense the red, more spicy the salsa; Levitan & Shermer, 2014) or
268 28 with the colour of the plate on which a food is served (being red the spiciest; Tu et al., 2016).

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276 29 In recent years there has been a growing interest in understanding shape symbolism within the
277 30 framework of flavour-vision correspondences (Becker et al., 2011; Velasco et al., 2014; Velasco,
278 31 Woods, Petit, et al., 2016). However, despite the burning sensation caused by pungent food being
279 32 considered a significant contributor to flavour perception, to date no study has analysed the
280 33 association between shapes and spiciness. Studies conducted so far show that rounded forms tend
281 34 to be associated with sweet tastes, while angular forms are more commonly associated with bitter or
282 35 acidic foods (Liang et al., 2013; Velasco et al., 2014; Velasco, Woods, Deroy, & Spence, 2015;
283 36 Velasco, Woods, Marks, Cheok, & Spence, 2016). For example, Ngo, Misra, & Spence (2011) asked
284 37 people to match shapes with chocolates varying in cocoa content (30, 70 or 90%) and found that
285 38 they associated flavours that are more bitter with more angular shapes, whereas Ngo et al. (2013)

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¹ Although the terms *spiciness* or *spicy* may also refer to the aroma of a given food (Spence et al., 2014), in the present paper they are used to describe the burning sensation caused by capsaicin (Caterina et al., 1997).

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1 demonstrated that people consistently match juices rated as sweet with rounder shapes and juices
2 that are considered sour with angular shapes. Other researchers have documented similar
3 crossmodal correspondences with more complex flavours such as cheeses. Gal, Wheeler, & Shiv
4 (2007) asked a group of participants to estimate the surface area of a series of geometric shapes
5 before evaluating a group of cheeses, and they found that participants who evaluated the surface
6 area of angular (rather than rounded) shapes perceived the cheese to taste sharper. Going one step
7 further, Spence, Ngo, Percival, & Smith (2013) analysed the shape symbolism of each flavour
8 component of different types of cheese (taste, smell, texture and overall flavour) and showed that
9 crossmodal correspondences were mainly based on the taste rather than the smell or the texture.
10 Associations have been documented even in flavours processed almost entirely by the trigeminal
11 system: two studies that analysed the case of carbonated water showed that still water was
12 consistently matched with rounded shapes while sparkling water was associated with angular shapes
13 (Ngo, Piqueras-Fiszman, & Spence, 2012; Spence & Gallace, 2011). Although recent studies have
14 challenged the idea that the same associations are universally shared and have suggested
15 differences between cultures (Bremner et al., 2013; Wan et al., 2014), on average these effects have
16 proven to be robust and consistent across products and groups of participants (Parise, 2016;
17 Spence, 2011). Since shapes can apparently influence the evaluation of food regardless of whether
18 they are seen before (Gal et al., 2007) or during consumption (Liang et al., 2013), one might expect
19 that the shape of an image shown on a package could influence consumer's spiciness expectations
20 (Velasco et al., 2014; Velasco, Woods, Petit, et al., 2016). Accordingly, we propose:

21 H1a. Spiciness will be associated with angular rather than with rounded shapes.

22 H1b. A product will be more easily associated with spiciness if the image depicted on its
23 package has an angular rather than a rounded shape.

24 2.3. Angularity as a cue for aggressiveness

25 The crossmodal matching between shapes and flavours may be explained by an affective
26 mechanism, as people's liking for a stimuli appear to influence their shape matching responses (for
27 flavour-shape affective correspondences, see Liang et al., 2013; Velasco et al., 2015; for odour-
28 shape affective correspondences see also Hanson-Vaux, Crisinel, & Spence, 2013; Seo et al., 2010).
29 Given that some researchers have proposed that the associations between stimuli from different
30 senses are mediated by emotion (Guerdoux, Trouillet, & Brouillet, 2014; Palmer, Schloss, Xu, &
31 Prado-Leon, 2013; Schifferstein & Tanudjaja, 2004), it has been suggested that sweet-rounded
32 correspondences and bitter/sour-angular correspondences may share an affective congruence in
33 which sweet tastes and rounded shapes are regarded as pleasant stimuli whereas bitter/sour tastes
34 and angular shapes are initially considered unpleasant stimuli (Bar & Neta, 2006; Steiner, 1974). In
35 fact, a large number of studies support the idea that while organic and rounded shapes are
36 considered pleasant and friendly, pointy shapes elicit threat and aggressiveness and are therefore
37 more commonly disliked (Bar & Neta, 2006; Carbon, 2010; Dazkir & Read, 2012; Ghoshal,
38 Boatwright, & Malika, 2015; Larson, Aronoff, & Stearns, 2007; Leder & Carbon, 2005; Westerman et
39 al., 2012). Two classical studies in this field showed that there is an association between the
40 aggressiveness of a concept and the angularity of the line chosen to represent it, as in both cases

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357 1 words like “hard”, “cruel” or “furious” were matched with angled lines more frequently than concepts
358 2 like “merry”, “weak” or “gentle”, which were consistently paired with rounded lines (Lundholm, 1921;
359 3 Poffenberger & Barrows, 1924). In a more recent study, Bar & Neta (2006) suggested that objects
360 4 with angled contours trigger a greater sense of threat than objects with rounded contours, and
361 5 demonstrate that the contour of an object has a critical role in people’s attitude towards it since
362 6 stimuli with rounded shapes were preferred to stimuli with angular shapes. The relation between
363 7 shapes and aggressiveness has been documented even in studies of human facial expression,
364 8 which suggest that diagonal and angular face patterns convey threat whereas round face patterns
365 9 evoke warmth (Aronoff, Woike, & Hyman, 1992). This association is implicit and automatic not only at
366 10 the cognitive level (Larson, Aronoff, & Steuer, 2012) but also at the physiological level, since a fMRI
367 11 test shows that an angular stimulus causes more activity in the amygdala than a rounded stimulus
368 12 (Bar & Neta, 2007).

373 13 Given the above, it has been argued that a reason by which angular shapes and bitter tastes are
374 14 commonly associated is because both stimuli evoke threat (Turoman, Velasco, Chen, Huang, &
375 15 Spence, 2018), as many natural poisons have a bitter taste (Garcia & Hankins, 1975; Lundström et
376 16 al., 2011). We hypothesize that this is also the case for spiciness, and we propose that spiciness and
377 17 angular shapes share a common cognitive space in which both stimuli are rendered as aggressive.
378 18 Indeed, some studies link spiciness and aggressiveness (Batra, Ghoshal, & Raghunathan, 2017).
379 19 The irritation produced by capsaicin leads to the characteristic burning sensation of spicy foods,
380 20 which has been related with discomfort or even pain (Bègue, Bricout, Boudesseul, Shankland, &
381 21 Duke, 2015; Byrnes & Hayes, 2013) and in turn may evoke aggressiveness (Berkowitz, 1990, 1993).
382 22 Therefore:

386 23 H2. The effect of shape angularity on spiciness expectations will be mediated by perceived
387 24 aggressiveness of the shape.

390 25 **3. Pretests**

392 26 3.1. Adequacy of the chosen stimulus

393 27 A fire icon depicted on the front of a bag of nuts was chosen as the stimulus for this experiment
394 28 under the assumption that it is a propositionally indeterminate visual sign which may evoke both
395 29 spicy and roasted meanings to the observer. To verify this assumption, a pretest was conducted in
396 30 which 31 participants (16 female, mean age 20.7 years) completed an open-ended task. Instructions
397 31 were given as follows: *“Imagine you are in a supermarket and you see a bag of nuts on which front
398 32 an icon of fire is depicted. When you see fire depicted on a nuts bag, you think it means the nuts
399 33 are...”*. The participants were asked to respond as quickly as possible. The elicited meanings were
400 34 *Spicy* (in Spanish, *Picantes*; N=18, 58.1%) and *Roasted* (in Spanish, *Tostados*; N=13, 41.9%). No
401 35 other words were elicited. The difference between the two percentages was not significant ($\chi^2=0.806$,
402 36 $p=0.37$), thus showing that a bag of nuts with a depiction of fire is adequate for this experiment since
403 37 the fire image can be interpreted in two different ways (i.e. that the nuts are spicy or that the nuts are
404 38 roasted).

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416 1 3.2. Effectiveness of the icons shape manipulation
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418 2 Once the adequacy of the stimulus had been checked, a total of eight fire icons varying only in their
419 3 shape were designed of which four were intended to be considered angular (A, B, C and D) and the
420 4 other four were intended to be rather perceived as rounded (E, F, G and H), see Fig. 1a. The stimuli
421 5 were designed with Adobe Illustrator CC 2017.1.0 (Adobe Systems Incorporated, 2006). Since the
422 6 shape of the image depicted on the packaging is the independent variable of this experiment, the
423 7 effectiveness of the shape manipulation was verified by conducting a pretest in which 35 participants
424 8 (20 female, mean age 23 years) evaluated the angularity of each of the eight fire icons. Adapting the
425 9 design of Spence & Gallace (2011), participants were given a sheet of paper with eight scales (four
426 10 randomly distributed on each side of the sheet) on which to place each of the fire icons (the scales
427 11 can be seen in Fig. 1b). The shapes depicted on each side of the scale are the ones commonly used
428 12 in this kind of experiments, representing an angular and a rounded shape on each end (Spence &
429 13 Gallace, 2011). Written instructions were provided as follows: *“Please indicate where each of this
430 14 icons would be for you on this scale. If you associate the icon more with the shape on the left, make
431 15 a mark in the left part of the scale. If you associate it more with the shape on the right, make a mark
432 16 in the right part of the scale. Draw the mark closer to a shape the clearer you see the association
433 17 with it.”* The scale was 10 cm long and had a vertical line marking the mid-point of the line.
434 18 Responses were measured using a ruler, assigning a value of zero to the mid-point of the scale.
435 19 Responses on the left half of the scale were registered as negative values and responses on the
436 20 right half as positive values. A one sample t-test was conducted with zero (the mid-point of the scale)
437 21 as the test value. Results show that each of the four fire icons designed to seem angular rather than
438 22 rounded were indeed more associated with the angular shape than with the rounded shape (A: $X_{\square}=-$
439 23 3.47 , $t(65)=-11.64$, $p<0.001$; B: $X_{\square}=-2.44$, $t(65)=-9.85$, $p<0.001$; C: $X_{\square}=-1.45$, $t(65)=-5.20$, $p<0.001$;
440 24 D: $X_{\square}=-1.09$, $t(65)=-4.86$, $p<0.001$) and that each of the four icons which shape was intended to be
441 25 considered more rounded than angular were more associated with the rounded rather than the
442 26 angular end of the scale (E: $X_{\square}=2.15$, $t(65)=12.42$, $p<0.001$; F: $X_{\square}=2.50$, $t(65)=9.72$, $p<0.001$; G:
443 27 $X_{\square}=2.71$, $t(65)=11.32$, $p<0.001$; H: $X_{\square}=3.49$, $t(65)=16.00$, $p<0.001$; see Fig. 1b).
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Fig. 1. (a) The eight fire icons designed as the stimuli for the experiment; (b) the eight scales used to measure the effectiveness of the icons shape manipulation. Each scale was 10 cm long. The vertical lines represent the mid-points of the scales. The participants' mean response \pm the standard deviation (SD) is represented above each scale.

Additionally, a Ward's hierarchical cluster analysis using squared Euclidean distances as proximity measures revealed that the four fire icons rated as angular made up a single angular icon cluster and that the four icons rated as rounded formed a unique rounded icon cluster (Table 1; see also Dendrogram in Fig. 2). According to this results, the four angular fire icons were henceforth analysed as a single 'angular' fire icons set and the four rounded fire icons as a single 'rounded' fire icons set.

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Table 1
 Ward's hierarchical cluster analysis

Stage	Cluster combined		Coefficients	Stage cluster first appears		Next stage
	Cluster 1	Cluster 2		Cluster 1	Cluster 2	
1	G	H	31,585	0	0	4
2	E	F	74,675	0	0	4
3	B	C	126,690	0	0	5
4	E	G	192,418	2	1	7
5	B	D	263,756	3	0	6
6	A	B	443,602	0	5	7
7	A	E	2218,866	6	4	0

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Fig. 2. Dendrogram obtained by means of Ward's hierarchical cluster analysis

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Eight bags of nuts varying only in the shape of the fire icon depicted on its front were created with Adobe Photoshop CC 2017.1.1 (Adobe Systems Incorporated, 2006) based on the findings from these pretests (Fig. 3).

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2 **Fig. 3.** Example of an angular fire icon (left) and a rounded fire icon (right) bag of nuts designed for
3 the experiment

4 **4. Materials and methods**

5 4.1. Participants

6 66 undergraduate students (35 female, mean age 20.7 years, $sd=2.49$) from Zaragoza University
7 took part in this experiment in exchange for being included in a raffle for gift vouchers in a well-known
8 online store. All the participants performed the experiment voluntarily and did not know the real
9 objectives of the study.

10 4.2. Apparatus and materials

11 The experiment took place in a quiet room with stable and homogeneous conditions of light and
12 temperature in the Escuela de Ingeniería y Arquitectura of Zaragoza University. Upon arrival, each
13 participant was seated in a single cubicle about 50cm in front of a 17" CRT monitor with a resolution
14 of 1366 x 768px and a refresh rate of 60Hz, and performed the experiment following the instructions
15 shown on the screen. The software used was OpenSesame 3.1.9 (Mathôt, Schreij & Theeuwes,
16 2012).

17 4.3. Design and procedure

18 The experiment was conducted following a within-subject design that was divided in three parts (Fig.
19 4). Part order was the same for all the participants. In the first part, the participants were asked to
20 indicate their association between spiciness and shape angularity. In the second part, they were
21 asked to rate the perceived aggressiveness of each of the eight fire icons designed as stimuli for the
22 experiment. The fire icons were displayed one at a time on the screen following a random order.
23 Then, the third task consisted on a speeded classification task in which the effect of the shape
24 angularity of the fire icons on sensory expectations was measured. Finally, demographic information
25 was collected and participants were thanked and debriefed. The experiment lasted from 10-15 min
26 per participant.

Fig. 4. Outline of the main study

4.4. Measures

4.4.1. Association between spiciness and shape angularity

The association between spiciness and shape angularity was measured by asking the participants to indicate where would they place spiciness on a scale with an angular shape at one end and a rounded shape at the other, following an identical design to that of the pretest described in section ‘3.2. Effectiveness of the icons shape manipulation’. Written instructions were provided as follows: “Please indicate where spiciness (in Spanish, *sabor picante*) would be for you on this scale. If you associate spiciness more with the shape on the left, make a mark in the left part of the scale. If you associate it more with the shape on the right, make a mark in the right part of the scale. Draw the mark closer to a shape the clearer you see the association with it.” The scale was 10 cm long and had a vertical line marking the mid-point of the line. Scale responses were measured using a ruler assigning a value of zero to the mid-point of the scale. Responses on the left half of the scale were registered as negative values and responses on the right half as positive values.

In addition, the participants were asked to indicate where would they place the roasted flavour (in Spanish, *sabor tostado*) on a second identical scale to check (1) if a crossmodal correspondence also exists between roasted flavour and shape angularity and (2) if so, to verify that it is not as strong as the one between shape angularity and spiciness. In this regard, the participants also performed a matching task in which they indicated which of the shapes displayed in the scale (the angular one or the rounded one) would they associate with spiciness and which one would they associate with the roasted flavour. The purpose of this task was to check if, when forced to decide, the participants would match the angular shape with spiciness and, consequently, the rounded shape with the roasted flavour.

4.4.2. Perceived aggressiveness of the fire icons

The perceived aggressiveness of each of the fire icons was measured according to a Likert scale of 1 (not aggressive at all) to 7 (strongly aggressive). In order to avoid priming (Johnston & Dark, 1986), participants also had to rate each icon according to three other concepts used as distractors.

4.4.3. Effect of the shape angularity of the fire icons on sensory expectations

The effect of the shape of the fire icons on consumer sensory expectations was implicitly measured by means of a speeded classification task. During this, following a design similar to that of the *taste response task* reported by Velasco, Woods, Marks, et al. (2016), the congruence between icon

1 shape and sensory expectations was manipulated and the participants had to categorise the eight
 2 bags of nuts used as stimuli as being spicy or roasted. Following our hypothesis, the congruent
 3 pairings were angular icons with spiciness and rounded icons with roasted flavour, while the
 4 incongruent pairings were rounded icons with spiciness and angular icons with roasted flavour. From
 5 now on, these pairings will be referred to as *Angular/Spicy*, *Rounded/Roasted*, *Rounded/Spicy* and
 6 *Angular/Roasted*, respectively.

7 At the beginning of each block, a screen with instructions was displayed indicating how the stimuli
 8 should be classified in the upcoming trials. Throughout each block, the target stimuli appeared (one
 9 at a time) in the centre of the screen and the words *Spicy* and *Roasted* remained visible to the left or
 10 right of the target stimulus. The participants had to respond as fast and accurately as possible by
 11 pressing the E or the I keys on the keyboard according to the correct mapping indicated in the block's
 12 instructions. If participants made an error, feedback of a red cross on the screen was shown during
 13 500 ms. The right-left position of *Spicy* and *Roasted* words was counterbalanced between blocks,
 14 thus generating four randomly ordered different blocks of trials. Each block consisted of 16 randomly
 15 ordered trials (with each stimulus repeated twice), giving rise to a total of 64 trials completed by each
 16 participant (Table 2). Block order was randomised across participants. The task was preceded by a
 17 set of 16 practice trials which were not analysed in order to familiarize participants with the
 18 procedure. The reaction times (RTs) of participants' responses were collected.

Table 2
 Summary of the blocks of the speeded classification task

Block	Congruence	Left response key	Right response key	Number of trials
1	Congruent pairings	Angular/Spicy	Rounded/Roasted	16
2	Reversed congruent pairings	Rounded/Roasted	Angular/Spicy	16
3	Incongruent pairings	Angular/Roasted	Rounded/Spicy	16
4	Reversed incongruent pairings	Rounded/Spicy	Angular/Roasted	16

19
 20 The implicit sensory associations for each set of fire icons (angular or rounded) was operationalized
 21 as Cohen's d_z standardized difference scores (Cohen, 1988, p. 48; cf. Lakens, 2013). Thus, Cohen's
 22 d_z score was calculated for the angular set of icons as the mean of the differences between the RTs
 23 of the *Angular/Spicy* and the *Angular/Roasted* trials divided by the standard deviation of those
 24 differences, while for the rounded set of icons it was calculated as the mean of the differences
 25 between the RTs of the *Rounded/Spicy* and the *Rounded/Roasted* trials divided by the standard
 26 deviation of those differences. By doing so, the lower the negative value, or the larger the positive
 27 value, the stronger the association with spiciness or roasted flavour, respectively. Note that these
 28 Cohen's d_z scores represent a measure of implicit expectations as they were calculated by using the
 29 RTs obtained in the speeded classification task, and that the participants were not explicitly asked
 30 about their sensory expectations.

31 4.5. Data analyses

32 Regarding the association between spiciness and shape angularity, a one sample t-test was
 33 conducted for each scale (spiciness and roasted flavour) with zero (the mid-point of the scale) as the
 34 test value in order to assess if there was a statistically significant association to one of the shapes of

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770 1 the scale. Additionally, a paired measures t-test was used to compare the position of each stimulus
771 2 on the scale in order to verify that both were sufficiently different from each other. A chi-square in
772 3 contingency tables was used to analyse the results of the matching task.

774
775 4 As for the speeded classification task, the RTs of the incorrect trials (i.e. wrong answers, 6.46% of
776 5 the responses) or which deviated by more than 3 standard deviations from the participants'
777 6 conditional mean (2.43% of the correct answers) were excluded from the analyses (Semin & Palma,
778 7 2014). Remaining data were first analysed in a 2 x 2 repeated measures ANOVA with the shape of
780 8 the fire icons (angular, rounded) and expectations (spicy, roasted) as the two factors and the mean
781 9 reaction time (RT) required to classify each nuts bag as the dependent variable. The aim of this
782 10 preliminary analysis was to check if an interaction existed so that the mean RTs of each of the four
783 11 combinations of trials (i.e. *Angular/Spicy*, *Rounded/Roasted*, *Rounded/Spicy* and *Angular/Roasted*)
784 12 could be analysed separately. Once that condition was fulfilled and the Cohen's d_z scores had been
786 13 calculated for both the angular and the rounded set of icons, a paired measures t-test was used to
787 14 compare them in order to assess if sensory expectations were influenced by the fire icons shapes.

789 15 Finally, a mediation analysis was conducted to investigate whether the effect of the icons' shape on
790 16 sensory expectations was mediated by the perceived aggressiveness of the icons. Mediation
792 17 analysis is a regression-based statistical method used to evaluate if an independent variable
793 18 influences a dependent variable through one or more other intervening variables (Hayes, 2009,
794 19 2018). In its simplest form, a simple mediation model is a causal system in which an independent
795 20 variable X is proposed to influence a dependent variable Y through a single mediating variable M,
797 21 thus allowing to assess the mechanism by which X exerts its effect on Y (Hayes, 2018). According to
798 22 our proposed model, an angular fire icon is considered more aggressive than a rounded fire icon,
799 23 which in turn raises spiciness (vs roasted flavour) expectations (being the opposite true for a rounded
800 24 fire icon). Hence, the shape of the fire icons (angular or rounded) was used as the two-condition
802 25 independent variable, the Cohen's d_z score was used as the dependent variable, and the mean
803 26 perceived aggressiveness of each fire icon set was used as the mediating variable. The analysis was
804 27 carried out using the MEMORE 1.1 macro for SPSS according to the method proposed for within-
806 28 subject experimental designs by Montoya & Hayes (2017). MEMORE is a macro for SPSS which
807 29 allows to easily implement the method described by Judd, Kenny, & McClelland (2001) by which
808 30 mediation analysis should be conducted in within-subject designs. Bias-corrected bootstrapping
809 31 (5000 samples) was used to calculate confidence intervals for the indirect effect.

811 32 Effects for the t-tests and the ANOVA were considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$. The
812 33 indirect effect of the mediation analysis was considered significant if it did not include zero (Montoya
814 34 & Hayes, 2017). Effect sizes for paired measures t tests were operationalized as Cohen's d_z
815 35 standardized difference scores (Cohen, 1988, p. 48). The data was processed and analysed by using
817 36 SPSS Statistics 23 (Armonk, NY, USA).

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829 **1 5. Results**

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831 **2 5.1. Association between spiciness and shape angularity**

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833 **3** An association exists between spiciness and angularity, as the participants judged spiciness as
834 **4** having a significantly pointy shape, $X_{\square} = -3.75$ cm, $t(65) = -37.16$, $p < 0.001$, supporting H1a. In contrast,
835 **5** roasted flavour was not found to be associated neither with the angular shape nor with the rounded
836 **6** shape, $X_{\square} = 0.09$ cm, $t(65) = 0.37$, $p = 0.71$. Thus, both stimulus were located on the scale in places
837 **7** significantly different from each other, $t(65) = 15.32$, $p < 0.001$, $d_z = 1.89$ (Fig. 5).

8

852 **9 Fig. 5.** Results of the association between spiciness/roasted flavour and shape angularity. Each
853 **10** scale was 10 cm long. The vertical lines represent the mid-point of the scales. The participants' mean
854 **11** response \pm the standard deviation (SD) for each stimulus are represented above the scales.

856 **12** The results of the matching task reinforce these findings and show that the angular shape is robustly
857 **13** matched with spiciness and, as a result, the rounded shape is matched with the roasted flavour
858 **14** (angular/spicy and rounded/roasted matches, respectively: $N = 63$, 95.4%; $\chi^2 = 54.545$, $p < 0.001$).
859 **15** These findings suggest that while the roasted flavour is not associated with any particular shape
860 **16** when assessed by itself, it is consistently paired with the rounded shape in a matching task due to
861 **17** the strong association that exists between spiciness and angular shapes.

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865 **18 5.2. Effect of the shape angularity of the fire icons on sensory expectations**

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867 **19** The results of the 2x2 repeated measures ANOVA show that the interaction between the shape of
868 **20** the fire icons and sensory expectations was significant, $F(1,65) = 27.44$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.30$, so the four
869 **21** combinations of trials (i.e. *Angular/Spicy*, *Rounded/Roasted*, *Rounded/Spicy* and *Angular/Roasted*)
870 **22** were analysed separately. As can be seen in Table 3, participants classified the angular fire icons
871 **23** significantly faster when they were associated with spiciness than when they were associated with
872 **24** the roasted flavour, $t(65) = 4.84$, $p < 0.001$, $d_z = 0.59$. Furthermore, participants classified the rounded
873 **25** fire icons significantly faster when they were associated with the roasted flavour than when they were
874 **26** associated with spiciness, $t(65) = -4.21$, $p < 0.001$, $d_z = -0.52$. No differences were found within the
875 **27** congruent pairing, $t(65) = -0.63$, $p = 0.53$, $d_z = -0.08$, nor within the incongruent pairing, $t(65) = -0.63$,
876 **28** $p = 0.53$, $d_z = -0.08$.

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880 **29** The shape angularity of the fire icons exerted an influence on sensory expectations, as the nuts'
881 **30** bags which displayed angular fire icons were associated with spiciness (Cohen's $d_z = -0.57$), and the

1 nuts' bags with rounded fire icons were conversely associated with the roasted flavour (Cohen's
 2 $d_z=0.42$), $t(65)=4.66$, $p<0.001$, $d_z=0.57$, supporting H1b.

Table 3
 Mean RTs obtained in the speeded classification task

Fire icons shape	Mean RTs in ms (SD)		Cohen's d_z
	Spicy	Roasted	
Angular	512 (79)	574 (127)	-0.57
Rounded	567 (147)	507 (74)	0.42

3
 4 5.3. Indirect effect of the shape angularity of the fire icons on sensory expectations through the fire
 5 icons' perceived aggressiveness

6 The results of the mediation analysis show that the fire icons' angularity indirectly influenced sensory
 7 expectations through its effect on how aggressive the fire icons' were perceived (Fig. 6), thus
 8 supporting H2. The indirect effect of the fire icons' shape on sensory expectations through the icons'
 9 perceived aggressiveness was statistically significant, with the 95% not containing zero (Bootstrap
 10 [5000] results: $B=-0.91$, $SE=0.35$, 95% CI [-1.56, -0.19]). The participants considered the angular fire
 11 icons as more aggressive than the rounded fire icons ($B=2.61$, $SE=0.15$, $p<0.001$), which in turn
 12 increased the expectations that the product was spicy rather than roasted ($B=-0.35$, $SE=0.17$,
 13 $p<0.05$). The direct effect of the fire icons' shape on sensory expectations was not significant ($B=-$
 14 0.08 , $SE=0.50$, $p=0.88$), suggesting that there was no evidence that the shape of the fire icons had
 15 an effect on sensory expectations regardless of its aggressiveness perception (Hayes, 2018).

16
 17 **Fig. 6.** Mediation of fire icons' perceived aggressiveness between fire icon's shape and sensory
 18 expectations (MEMORE 1.1, number of bootstraps=5000; Montoya & Hayes, 2017). *Note:* Negative
 19 values in the dependent variable represent a stronger association with spiciness rather than with
 20 roasted flavour, while the opposite is true for positive values. Coding=angular (1), rounded (0); B
 21 (SE)=path coefficient (standard error); * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

22 **6. Discussion**

23 This research assessed if the crossmodal correspondence between spiciness and shapes could be
 24 used to modulate how people interpret an ambiguous image depicted on food packaging. To that
 25 end, the association between spiciness and angular shapes was studied, and a response time-based
 26 experiment was conducted on which it was assessed if the spiciness expectations of a bag of nuts
 27 could be enhanced by manipulating the angularity of a fire icon depicted on its front. The results
 28 indicate that the packages displaying angular fire icons enhanced spiciness expectations, whereas

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947 1 the packages with rounded fire icons were more easily associated with the roasted flavour. This
948 2 influence was mediated by the perceived aggressiveness of the icons, so that a pointy fire icon
949 3 raised spiciness expectations through a higher aggressiveness perception.

951
952 4 This investigation can be framed in the literature related to the influence of visual extrinsic cues on
953 5 consumer expectations and response to food, where the effect of factors such as packaging shape
954 6 (Becker et al., 2011; Overbeeke & Peters, 1991; Rebollar, Lidón, Serrano, Martín, & Fernández,
955 7 2012; Smets & Overbeeke, 1995), packaging colours (Piqueras-Fizman & Spence, 2011; Spence,
956 8 2018; Tijssen, Zandstra, de Graaf, & Jager, 2017) or packaging images (Lidón, Rebollar, Gil-Pérez,
957 9 Martín, & Vicente-Villardón, in press; Rebollar et al., 2016, 2017; Smith et al., 2015; Szocs &
958 10 Lefebvre, 2016) has been analysed (see Piqueras-Fizman & Spence, 2015; and Velasco, Woods,
959 11 Petit, et al., 2016, for reviews). As we will discuss here, the findings of this research contribute to the
960 12 literature in two ways. First, these results go a step further in the field of crossmodal
961 13 correspondences by documenting an association between spiciness and pointy shapes and
962 14 suggesting that it is mediated through affective evaluation. Second, we show that these findings can
963 15 be implemented in the field of semiotics in order to help packaging designers and producers to
964 16 convey the right messages to the consumer, as one of the possible interpretations of an image
965 17 displayed on a packaging may be favoured by manipulating the image's shape.

970 18 The results of this study contribute to the research of crossmodal correspondences showing that an
971 19 association exists between spiciness and pointy shapes. Although this association had never been
972 20 empirically tested before, there were grounds to think that pointy shapes and spiciness may be
973 21 matched in consumers' mind (Blazhenkova & Kumar, 2018; Wang et al., 2017). Indeed, this result is
974 22 in line with previous studies that have documented associations between spiciness and cues from
975 23 other sensory domains such as audition (Wang et al., 2017) or sight (Levitan & Shermer, 2014; Tu et
976 24 al., 2016). For example, Seo et al. (2010) demonstrated that the smell of pepper (which, according to
977 25 Wang et al. (2017), is an approximate olfactory counterpart to the trigeminal spicy sensation) is more
978 26 associated with angular shapes rather than with rounded shapes. Given that olfaction plays a key
979 27 role in the perception of flavour (Spence, Smith, & Auvray, 2014; Spence, 2015), it is not surprising
980 28 that this association also occurs when thinking about other flavour contributors such as the burning
981 29 sensation caused by capsaicin (Lawless, 1989; Charles Spence, 2015b). In this regard, it may be
982 30 argued that this association could have been driven based either on trigeminal cues or aromas, as
983 31 the term *spiciness* may refer to both. Spiciness is a sensation that can contribute to flavour
984 32 perception (Lawless, 1989; Spence, 2015b). *Spicy* may be sometimes, and for some, equivalent to
985 33 painful, warm, irritating, burning (Bègue et al., 2015; Caterina et al., 1997). One may think that since
986 34 in our main study there were two types of shapes and two sensory descriptors, the correspondence
987 35 could have been driven based either on trigeminal cues or aromas. However, we propose that the
988 36 correspondence is more trigeminal-based since spiciness was highly associated with the angular
989 37 shape, but the roasted flavour (when assessed by itself) was not particularly associated to a shape.
990 38 In addition, the fact that the effect was mediated by aggressiveness supports the notion that the
991 39 difference is more based on trigeminal associations, since the concept of "roasted aroma" in this food
992 40 context cannot be painful (nor linked to aggressiveness).

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1006 1 Furthermore, our results indicate that the association between spiciness and pointy shapes is
1007 2 affectively mediated, since perceived aggressiveness of the icons designed to convey sensory
1008 3 information increased spiciness expectations. This supports the notion that crossmodal
1009 4 correspondences between flavours and shapes may be, at least to some extent, explained in terms
1010 5 of affective mediation (Guerdoux et al., 2014; Palmer et al., 2013; Schifferstein & Tanudjaja, 2004),
1011 6 and is in line with previous findings that suggest that both pointy shapes and spiciness share a
1012 7 common affective space in which both stimuli are rendered as unpleasant or aggressive: whilst
1013 8 pointy shapes are generally associated with dangerous objects (Ghoshal et al., 2015) or even angry
1014 9 faces (Aronoff et al., 1992) and therefore are initially disliked in comparison with rounded shapes
1015 10 (Bar & Neta, 2006), the burning trigeminal sensation produced by the capsaicin of spicy food has
1016 11 been related to discomfort, unpleasantness or pain (Bègue et al., 2015; Byrnes & Hayes, 2013;
1017 12 Caterina et al., 1997). Thus, the results of this research add to those of other studies which suggest
1018 13 that the mechanism behind the crossmodal correspondence between flavour and shapes is of an
1019 14 affective nature and do not fit satisfactorily into any of the three kinds of crossmodal
1020 15 correspondences previously proposed in the literature (i.e. statistical, structural or semantic; Spence,
1021 16 2011). Indeed, the studies that have assessed separately the association between abstract shapes
1022 17 and each of the sensory components of flavour perception (i.e. taste, smell or trigeminal; Spence et
1023 18 al., 2014) appear to be in the same line, as is the case with taste-shape correspondences (Liang et
1024 19 al., 2013; Velasco et al., 2015), odour-shape correspondences (Hanson-Vaux et al., 2013; Seo et al.,
1025 20 2010) or trigeminal-shape correspondences (Spence et al., 2014): the mechanism behind these
1026 21 correspondences seems to work indirectly through emotion rather than through environmental or
1027 22 language inferences (cf. Turoman, Velasco, Chen, Huang, & Spence, 2018). However, note that it
1028 23 seems unlikely that the association between spiciness and pointy shapes is exclusively mediated by
1029 24 an affective evaluation: although the evidence suggesting that affective judgements play an important
1030 25 role in the matching between different stimuli across the senses related to flavour perception is
1031 26 strong, other still unknown mechanisms may also be at play (Turoman et al., 2018). In this regard,
1032 27 both the literature on shapes and motivation (Velasco, Salgado-Montejo, et al., 2016) and the
1033 28 literature on embodiment and grounded cognition (Salgado-Montejo, Tapia Leon, Elliot, Salgado, &
1034 29 Spence, 2015; Te Vaarwerk, van Rompay, & Okken, 2015) may offer alternative explanations for the
1035 30 findings reported here. While the shapes and motivation approach argues that people tend to avoid
1036 31 negatively-valenced stimuli and to approach positively-valenced stimuli (Krieglmeyer, Deutsch, de
1037 32 Houwer, & de Raedt, 2010; although the association between angular shapes and
1038 33 approach/avoidance motivation is yet not completely understood, e.g. Palumbo, Ruta, & Bertamini,
1039 34 2015; Velasco, Salgado-Montejo, et al., 2016), embodiment assumes that people interpret abstract
1040 35 concepts in terms of everyday physical interactions (Lakoff & Johnson, 1999). As stated by Fenko &
1041 36 van Rompay (2018), embodied cognition commonly assumes that the representation of symbolic
1042 37 concepts is grounded in direct bodily experience with the physical world. For example, abstract
1043 38 concepts like *importance* and *dominance* are processed in terms of physical properties such as
1044 39 *weight* and *height*, as people tend to relate the heaviness of an object and its perceived importance
1045 40 (Jostmann, Lakens, & Schubert, 2009) or the relative height of a product and its perceived
1046 41 dominance (van Rompay, Hekkert, Saakes, & Russo, 2005). Thus, according to this approach the
1047 42 association between spiciness and pointy shapes could also be explained because both concepts
1048 43 are structured under a similar underlying schema (van Rompay, Hekkert, & Muller, 2005): Since early

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1065 1 childhood we learn that physical and tactile interactions with angular objects may produce harm or
1066 2 pain on our skin, in the same way as spicy food may produce a similar sensation inside the mouth
1067 3 (Bègue et al., 2015; Caterina et al., 1997). Furthermore, it is worth mentioning that while
1068 4 aggressiveness is commonly related to threat and is thus initially disliked (Berkowitz, 1990; Liu,
1069 5 2004), that does not necessarily mean that it will be always processed as a negative input
1070 6 (Landwehr, McGill, & Herrmann, 2011). As is the case with other initially disliked stimuli as angular
1071 7 shapes or bitter flavours, in some contexts the concept of aggressiveness may be linked to positive
1072 8 judgements and therefore may be rendered as positive (Ghoshal et al., 2015; Landwehr et al., 2011).

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1076 9 From a semiotic point of view, the main contribution of this paper is that it shows that when it comes
1077 10 to convey sensory information about a product though an image depicted on its packaging, the
1078 11 reported crossmodal correspondence between spiciness and shapes can be used to favour one of
1079 12 the image's possible interpretations. Although this possibility has been somewhat suggested by
1080 13 previous researchers (Ngo et al., 2012; Velasco, Woods, Petit, et al., 2016), this is the first study that
1081 14 specifically addresses it experimentally by manipulating the shape of an image depicted on a
1082 15 package. This finding can be framed on both the two lines of analysis proposed in the literature that
1083 16 seek to understand the factors by which an indeterminate stimulus evokes a particular meaning: the
1084 17 slot/filler approach and the analogy approach (Smith et al., 2015). The slot/filler approach assumes
1085 18 that the probabilities of opting for one of the possible meanings of the sign (filler) will be greater the
1086 19 better it fits with any of the possible attributes of the object (slot) (Fillmore & Baker, 2010; Lynott &
1087 20 Connell, 2010; Smith, Osherson, Rips, & Keane, 1988), while the analogy approach states that the
1088 21 interpretation that has proved valid in similar past combinations will be preferred (Estes & Jones,
1089 22 2006; Gagné & Spalding, 2006; van Jaarsveld, Coolen, & Schreuder, 1994; see also Gregan-Paxton
1090 23 & John, 1997). The results of this investigation show that the shape of the image plays a role in these
1091 24 mechanisms, as it helps to evoke meaning by making a certain association more accessible in the
1092 25 mind of the consumer. Thus, according to the slot/filler approach, the results of this experiment can
1093 26 be explained as that an angular fire icon is associated with spiciness through an affective
1094 27 mechanism, so the concept *spicy* becomes more accessible to the consumer and therefore the
1095 28 chances of choosing it are increased. In addition, the existence of a crossmodal correspondence
1096 29 between spiciness and angular shapes implies that these results can also be explained under the
1097 30 analogy approach, since both spicy and pointy stimulus are consistently paired in consumers' mind
1098 31 as a congruent match. Overall, these findings show that when it comes to convey spiciness
1099 32 information about a product, images' shape angularity may be used besides other well-known signs
1100 33 such as textual claims or graphical scales (like the chillies scales commonly used in food packaging,
1101 34 where the higher the number of chillies shown, the spicier the food is supposed to be). Indeed, given
1102 35 the influence of sign congruency on consumer attitude (Becker et al., 2011), designers should be
1103 36 careful to ensure that all signs on the packaging send a consistent message.

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1112 37 However, as is the case in other works related to the study of crossmodal correspondences, the
1113 38 question arises as to what extent it is an association produced automatically in the mind of the
1114 39 consumer or, on the contrary, it rather emanates from a strategic process (Spence & Deroy, 2013).
1115 40 Some authors warn of the need to quantify the degree of automatism of the correspondences instead
1116 41 of adopting a two-pronged approach between bottom-up and top-down processes (Getz & Kubovy,

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1124 1 2018), and highlight the lack of consensus regarding what characteristics a process should have in
1125 2 order to be considered automatic (Spence & Deroy, 2013). Although conducting a speeded
1126 3 classification task allows to minimize the degree of reasoned processing (De Houwer, Teige-
1128 4 Mocigemba, Spruyt, & Moors, 2009), it is important to be cautious when drawing conclusions about
1129 5 the true nature of this correspondence since it has been shown that a lot of processes occur in the
1130 6 milliseconds in which the participant takes time to respond (Fiebelkorn, Foxe, & Molholm, 2010;
1131 7 Horowitz, Wolfe, Alvarez, Cohen, & Kuzmova, 2009; Spence & Deroy, 2013) and recent research
1133 8 has suggested that crossmodal correspondences may not be absolute in nature and may rather be
1134 9 subjected to the specific configuration of the task (Brunetti, Indraccolo, Gatto, & Spence, 2017).

1136 10 Beyond its contributions, this study has some limitations that must be taken into account. For
1137 11 example, there may be a bias regarding the diversity and features of the participants. Sample size
1138 12 was modest and all participants were university students living in the same country (Spain); as a
1139 13 result, further testing would be needed to see if these results could be extrapolated to other markets
1141 14 and other cohorts of consumers. In this regard, note that although some studies have found
1142 15 differences among populations (Bremner et al., 2013), crossmodal correspondences are shared by a
1144 16 large number of people (Spence, 2011). Indeed, few studies have been conducted to date studying
1145 17 individual differences (Parise, 2016). However, one may wonder if the semantic interpretation of the
1146 18 symbols displayed on product packaging would be different regarding consumer's culture and
1148 19 language, given that some studies suggest that structural differences between languages based on
1149 20 ideographic writing systems (e.g. Chinese) and western languages may influence packaging
1150 21 perception (Hoon Ang, 1997; Schmitt, Pan, & Tavassoli, 1994). A similar question arises regarding
1151 22 not only how people interpret symbols according to the structure of their language, but also according
1152 23 to their culture. Whereas for the participants in this study the depiction of an icon of fire in the context
1154 24 of food elicited the meaning of spiciness, this may not be the case across different cultures or
1155 25 consumer cohorts. Although the metaphor *spicy food is fire* relays on a sensation emerging directly
1156 26 from the sensory domain (Caterina et al., 1997; Tu et al., 2016), and may therefore be considered
1158 27 more stable across cultures than other kind of metaphors (e.g. linguistic metaphors, Landau, Meier,
1159 28 & Keefer, 2010), previous studies have suggested that the existence of individual differences should
1160 29 not be disregarded even within the same cultural group (Piqueras-fiszman, Ares, & Varela, 2011).

1162 30 Moreover, although in this type of study it is very difficult to completely isolate the study variable and
1163 31 there is a risk that part of the effects reported here are not exclusively due to the angularity of the
1164 32 icons but to another factor, the icons were designed as similar as possible in terms of size, symmetry
1165 33 and colour (Parise, 2016). Despite this, it could be argued that they are not only differentiated by
1166 34 angularity but also by other factors such as complexity, symmetry or colour, which in turn could have
1167 35 influenced the results (Turoman et al., 2018). Therefore, it cannot be ruled out that other factors
1170 36 besides angularity may have had an effect on the findings reported in this study, which leaves the
1171 37 door open to further research. On the other hand, despite the fact that participants did not know the
1172 38 true aim of the study, it should be noted that the order of the different experiment parts may have
1173 39 primed the responses for the subsequent tasks by making some concepts (namely, aggressiveness)
1174 40 more accessible in participants' minds. Priming is said to occur when one stimulus affects how a
1175 41 subsequent stimulus is processed (Johnston & Dark, 1986), so asking the participants to rate the

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1183 1 perceived aggressiveness of each of the fire icons used as stimuli in the speeded classification task
1184 2 may have biased their responses. To prevent this, the participants had also to evaluate each fire icon
1185 3 with respect to three other concepts not related to the objectives of the study (which were used as
1187 4 distractors). However, despite this precaution, the presence of a priming effect cannot be completely
1188 5 ruled out. Furthermore, the crossmodal association between spiciness and angular shapes was
1189 6 studied by using the spicy word and not by tasting spicy samples of food. Further research is thus
1190 7 needed in order to assess if this correspondence also occurs with tastants and not only with words
1192 8 (Velasco, Woods, Marks, et al., 2016).

1194 9 The work presented in this paper can be further developed through future lines of research. For
1195 10 example, this study did not analyse the effect of the fire icons shape on consumer affective response.
1196 11 It would be reasonable to expect that a higher perceived aggressiveness would lead to a positive
1197 12 attitude towards the product for consumers who like spicy food, while the opposite would be
1199 13 expected for people who does not like the burning sensation produced by pungent food. It would also
1200 14 be interesting to assess how the findings reported here relate to other signs commonly used to
1201 15 indicate the degree of spiciness of a food, such as chillies scales: according to our findings, one
1203 16 might think that the manipulation of the chillies' shape may be used to modulate spiciness
1204 17 expectations conveyed by the scale. In addition, the scope of this research was limited to studying
1205 18 the effect of manipulating the shape of an icon of fire depicted on a package on consumer
1206 19 expectations. The next logical step would be to assess if the shape manipulation also has an effect
1207 20 on sensory perception and on the hedonic response to the product, as other studies in this field
1209 21 suggest (Becker et al., 2011; Velasco et al., 2015). Moreover, it should be taken into account that
1210 22 while in this paper spiciness has been treated as if it was a single stimulus, in reality there are many
1211 23 kinds of spiciness differentiated in their intensity, their duration, and in the location of the trigeminal
1213 24 system receptors that react in contact with capsaicin (Baron & Penfield, 1996; Caterina et al., 1997;
1214 25 Prescott & Stevenson, 1995). Therefore, a next study should consider these differences by analysing
1215 26 their effect on the crossmodal correspondence between spiciness and abstract shapes.

1217 27 **7. Conclusion**

1219 28 For the consumer, correctly interpreting the visual signs depicted on food packaging is key to set the
1220 29 right sensory expectations. However, since an image can evoke different meanings in a given
1222 30 context, it is not easy for the designer to anticipate how the consumer will interpret it. The results of
1223 31 this investigation shed light in this subject showing that designers can communicate sensory
1224 32 information about the product just by manipulating the shape of the images depicted on the
1225 33 packaging. Specifically, it shows that while it is possible to communicate that a bag of nuts is spicy
1227 34 through a pointy fire icon (since the consumer implicitly associates spiciness and pointy shapes
1228 35 because both stimuli are rendered as aggressive), if the same bag of nuts displays a rounded fire
1229 36 icon the consumer rather interprets that the product have been roasted. Overall, these findings
1231 37 suggest that if a designer has to convey that the product contained in a package is spicy, it may be a
1232 38 good idea to do so by depicting angular images or pointy shapes rather than by depicting rounded
1233 39 shapes. This paper thus shows a useful way to implement the theoretical advances made to date
1234 40 regarding the crossmodal correspondence between spiciness and abstract shapes. This is of great

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1 interest to producers and food packaging designers as it can help them to better communicate the
2 desired message to consumers.

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Table 1

Ward's hierarchical cluster analysis

Stage	Cluster combined		Coefficients	Stage cluster first appears		Next stage
	Cluster 1	Cluster 2		Cluster 1	Cluster 2	
1	G	H	31,585	0	0	4
2	E	F	74,675	0	0	4
3	B	C	126,690	0	0	5
4	E	G	192,418	2	1	7
5	B	D	263,756	3	0	6
6	A	B	443,602	0	5	7
7	A	E	2218,866	6	4	0

Table 2

Summary of the blocks of the speeded classification task

Block	Congruence	Left response key	Right response key	Number of trials
1	Congruent pairings	Angular/Spicy	Rounded/Roasted	16
2	Reversed congruent pairings	Rounded/Roasted	Angular/Spicy	16
3	Incongruent pairings	Angular/Roasted	Rounded/Spicy	16
4	Reversed incongruent pairings	Rounded/Spicy	Angular/Roasted	16

Table 3

Mean RTs obtained in the speeded classification task

Fire icons shape	Mean RTs in ms (SD)		Cohen's d_z
	Spicy	Roasted	
Angular	512 (79)	574 (127)	-0.57
Rounded	567 (147)	507 (74)	0.42